

DESIGNING OF ELECTRICAL VEHICLE CHARGER USING MATLAB

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Abstract: Due to their reduced environmental effect and lower operating costs when compared to conventional gasoline-powered vehicles, electric vehicles (EVs) are becoming more and more popular. However, the absence of a thorough charging infrastructure prevents the wide-scale adoption of EVs. Therefore, creating effective and efficient EV chargers is essential for the market's success. A MATLAB-based simulation of an EV charger is described in this project. A power electronic converter, a control algorithm, and a battery management system are all included in the simulation model. In order to charge the EV battery, the converter transforms AC electricity from the grid into DC power. The charging of the battery is made safe and effective by the control algorithm. The battery management system keeps an eye on how fully charged the battery is and guards against either overcharging or undercharging. The simulation model is tested under different scenarios, including varying input voltages and loads, and the performance is evaluated in terms of charging time and efficiency. The simulation results show that the designed charger is capable of charging an EV battery within a reasonable time while maintaining a high level of efficiency. Overall, this project demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of using MATLAB to design and simulate an EV charger. The simulation results can be used to optimize the charger's design and improve its performance, leading to the development of more efficient and reliable EV charging systems

Keywords: Electric vehicle, Electrical vehicle supply equipment (EVSE), DC-DC Converter, Lithium battery, transformer, EV charger, car.

I. INTRODUCTION

The infrastructure required to accommodate the increasing number of electric vehicles on the road today must include an EV charger. Electric cars (EVs) are a more and more common choice for drivers as the need for environmentally friendly transportation options rises.[1] However, a strong charging infrastructure is necessary to guarantee that drivers have access to dependable and practical charging options in order to fully realize the potential of EVs.

A device called an electric car charger provides electric energy to an electric vehicle so that it can recharge its batteries.[2] A charging cable is normally used to connect the car to the charging station during the charging process to transfer electrical energy from the power grid to the batteries of the electric vehicle. An electric vehicle (EV) charger is an apparatus that provides electric energy to an EV to recharge its batteries.[3] A charging cable is normally used to connect the car to the charging station during the charging process to transfer electrical energy from the power grid to the batteries of the electric vehicle.

There are several different types of EV chargers, including Level 1, Level 2, and Level 3 (sometimes referred to as DC fast charging) chargers, each of which has a different charging rate and power required.[4] An electric car can be fully charged in as little as 24 hours using level 1 chargers, which are generally used for home charging. In public spaces like parking lots, workplaces, and retail malls, level 2 chargers can offer quicker charging times. The quickest and most potent chargers are Level 3 chargers, which can recharge an electric car in as little as 30 minutes. The demand for EV charging infrastructure has expanded as a result of the expansion of the EV market. [5]Investments in EV charging infrastructure are being made by governments, companies, and private citizens in order to facilitate the switch to electric mobility and lower emissions from fossil fuel-powered vehicles.

Range anxiety, or the worry that an EV will run out of power before reaching its destination, is one of the major obstacles to the general adoption of EVs. [6] It is essential to have a robust charging infrastructure if you want to allay this worry and give drivers the assurance they need to move to EVs. There are several places where charging infrastructure can be installed, including homes, offices, public parking lots, and roads.[7] The most typical way to charge an EV is at home, but public charging stations are becoming more and more prevalent.

II RELATED WORK

Fig.1 single phase full wave converter

Fig.2 output waveform for single phase full wave converter

The output dc voltage across the resistive load is given by

$$V_{0(av)} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T v_o(\omega t) d\omega t \tag{1}$$

$$V_{0(av)} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\alpha}^{\pi+\alpha} V_m \sin \omega t \tag{2}$$

$$d\omega t = \frac{V_m}{\pi} \left[-\cos \omega t \right]_{\alpha}^{\pi+\alpha} \tag{3}$$

$$V_0 = \frac{2V_m}{\pi} \cos \alpha \tag{4}$$

Fig.3 output waveform of single phase inverter

$$V_{0(rms)} = \left[\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T V_o^2(\omega t) d\omega t \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{4}$$

$$V_{0(rms)} = \left\{ \frac{1}{T} \left[\int_0^{\frac{T}{2}} V_s^2 dt + \int_{\frac{T}{2}}^T (-V_s)^2 dt \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{5}$$

$$= \left\{ \frac{V_s^2}{T} \left[\int_0^{\frac{T}{2}} dt + \int_{\frac{T}{2}}^T dt \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} = V_s \tag{6}$$

III PROPOSED WORK

Fig.4 control scheme

The above circuit diagram shows the proposed bidirectional digital control system, to obtain high power factor and loosely adjust the dc-link voltage at a high voltage (500 V), the controller for the ac/dc stage is employed. The voltage loop and current loop both control the I_{ac} and V_{dc} for the ac/dc stage, respectively. The measured V_{dc} and reference V_{dc_ref} are compared in the voltage loop. After that, a notch filter is used to remove the ripple at 120 Hz from the error signal. The ac voltage loop compensator H_{v_ac} processes the filtered error signal. The sinusoidal reference for the inner current loop will be produced by multiplying the compensator output V_c by the PLL output. It is simpler to construct a compensator since the transfer function won't be affected by variations in the dc link voltage thanks to the term $1/V_{dc}$'s use in the current loop to cancel the coupled term in the power stage transfer function. The disturbance from the input voltage V_{ac} is compensated for by the feed forward term V_{ac}/V_{dc} and the current loop compensator H_{i_ac} . Explaining the terms below there are,

Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor is referred to as IGBT. It is an electric 3-terminal semiconductor device with quick switching capabilities and great efficiency. The two primary purposes of a transistor, a tiny electronic component, are as follows. It can boost signals and serves as a switch for lighting circuits. Depending on their additional utility or particular use, transistors can be classified into various categories. IGBT, MOSFETs, and BJT (Bipolar Junction Transistor) are the most widely utilized transistors. Each has its preferences and advantages over the other, including BJTs and MOSFETs. Low switching loss, high I/P impedance, and the absence of secondary breakdown make MOSFETs superior than BJTs, which favor low on-state drops. The IGBT combines the BJT and MOSFET in a way that maximizes the performance of each transistor. High-pass filters are a particular kind of filter that rejects all low-frequency signals while allowing high-frequency signals to pass through without any amplitude attenuation. Signals with frequencies lower than the filter's cut-off frequency are blocked. While all signals that are higher in frequency than the cut-off frequency pass through with their full amplitude.

PLL (PHASE- LOCKED LOOP)

The phase and frequency of the input signal are tracked using a phase-locked loop. For synchronous communication, it is a really helpful tool. In the receiver, the PLL generates a coherent carrier signal for demodulation after acquiring the carrier frequency in the suppressed carrier mode of transmission. Like a normal feedback mechanism, a PLL functions. It adjusts the output frequency of the VCO until it syncs with the input signal, or until it matches the frequency of the input signal.

Fig.5 Circuit diagram of LLC filter

GPWM (Giga pulse width modulation)

Gigabit Pulse Width Modulation is known as G PWM. It is a technology that enables the adjustment of a fan's or a pump's speed by altering the width of the power pulses that are sent to it. This is accomplished by employing an integrated circuit to regulate the fan's or pump's speed and, consequently, the amount of cooling the CPU or GPU receives.

The best all-around option for all edits and effects is the H Delay analogue echo processor. You can utilise a variety of its effects, including delay and modulation, to change the sound of your audio. It also includes a noise-reduction tool that successfully mutes the noise in your vocals. You can add effects, such delay, to any specific section of your song with the H Delay analogue echo processor. Additionally, you can select the degree of the effect. You may adjust the amount of delay using the H Delay analogue echo processor. You can tune the delay time in milliseconds, just like the echoboy processor, to get flawless vocals. There is a display window included with it where you may enter the timing of any impact.

IV SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig.6 Matlab simulation diagram

The above figure shows the simulink model of Electrical hybrid vechile chargerin this circuit diagram, the DC input is connected to a bridge rectifier circuit, which is composed of four IGBT or an MOSFET. The diodes are arranged in a bridge configuration, which allows the DC input to be converted to the pulsating DC voltage.

The bridge rectifier is connected to the transformer, the transformer allows the DC-DC converter to provide isolation between the input and output circuits, which is useful for applications where there is a need to protect sensitive electronic components from voltage transients or electrical noise. Additionally, transformers can improve the efficiency of the DC-DC converter by reducing losses due to resistive elements in the circuit.

The output of the bridge rectifier circuit is then connected to a DC-DC converter circuit, which is composed of an inductor, a capacitor, and a switch. The switch is typically a Diodes, which allows the DC voltage to be converted into a high-frequency AC voltage.

The inductor and capacitor are used to filter the AC voltage and produce a smooth DC voltage at the output. Overall, the EHV charger model is a simple circuit that uses a bridge rectifier circuit and a DC-DC converter circuit to convert AC power into DC power and then boost the DC voltage to recharge the battery of the EHV.

Fig.7 switching pulses

Fig. 7 shows the output of DC converter when switch 1 and 3 in ON position its starts from 0(zero) position, and other switches in off mode. And when switch 2 and 4 in ON position its starts from 1(one) position, and other switches in off mode.

Fig.8 Battery performance waveforms

Fig. 8 shows the output of the battery, the battery output of an EHV charger refers to the voltage and current that the charger supplies to the battery of an electric vehicle during the charging process.

SoC (State of Charge) refers to the amount of charge that is currently stored in a battery, SOC can be determined by measuring the voltage, current and temperature of the battery.

It is not accurate to say that the battery current in an EHV (Extreme High Voltage) charger is negative. In fact, the battery current in an EHV charger can be either positive or negative, depending on whether the battery is being charged or discharged.

Fig.9 PWM pulses for inverter

Fig. 9 shows the input voltage to a different DC output voltage. The output voltage can be either higher or lower than the input voltage, depending on the type of DC to DC converter.

The output of a DC to DC converter can be explained in terms of its voltage regulation and ripple voltage.

Voltage regulation refers to the ability of the DC to DC converter to maintain a stable output voltage despite changes in the input voltage or load. A well-designed DC to DC converter will have a high level of voltage regulation, ensuring that the output voltage remains within a tight range of values.

Ripple voltage is a measure of the fluctuations in the output voltage caused by the switching action of the DC to DC converter. As the converter switches the input voltage on and off to generate the output voltage, small fluctuations in the output voltage can occur, which is called ripple voltage. The amount of ripple voltage present in the output of a DC to DC converter depends on the type of converter, the switching frequency, and the load.

Fig.10 inverter output waveform

The above figure shows the transformer primary voltage, the transformer is designed to step up the voltage of the input power supply to the required EHV level.

The primary voltage of a transformer in an EHV charger refers to the voltage level on the input side of the transformer. The input power supply is usually at a lower voltage level than the desired EHV level, so the transformer is used to step up the voltage to the required level. The primary voltage rating of the transformer is determined based on the input voltage level of the power supply.

Fig.11 reference and battery output voltage

Fig. 11 shows the output voltage of a DC to DC converter depends on the specific design of the converter and can be either higher or lower than the input voltage. The output voltage of a DC to DC converter can also be regulated by using a feedback mechanism. A feedback mechanism compares the output voltage to a reference voltage and adjusts the duty cycle of the switch to maintain a constant output voltage even if there are variations in the input voltage or load.

V CONCLUSION

Since the use of electric vehicles is growing daily, it is essential that their charging systems be strong and dependable so that users can drive electric vehicles without any issues. For charging plug-in hybrid electric automobiles, the article provides conductive AC charging procedures. In this study, the theory of conductive charging is examined, and a thorough examination of the on-board charger is performed, allowing one to confirm the legal states for the beginning of charging and the range of the maximum current limit, which is dictated by duty cycle. In accordance with standards set by the automotive industry, this document demonstrates how to construct conductive charging systems.

REFERENCES

- [1]. M. Salem et al., "Three-Phase Series Resonant DC-DC Boost Converter With Double LLC Resonant Tanks and Variable Frequency Control," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 22386-22399, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2969546.
- [2]. H. -J. Choi, K. -W. Heo and J. -H. Jung, "A Hybrid Switching Modulation of Isolated Bidirectional DC-DC Converter for Energy Storage System in DC Microgrid," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 6555-6568, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3138988.
- [3]. S. A. Gorji, H. G. Sahebi, M. Ektesabi and A. B. Rad, "Topologies and Control Schemes of Bidirectional DC-DC Power Converters: An Overview," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 117997-118019, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2937239
- [4]. M. V. Soares and Y. R. de Novaes, "MMC Based Hybrid Switched Capacitor DC-DC Converter," in *IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 3, pp. 142-152, 2022, doi: 10.1109/OJPEL.2022.3154726.
- [5]. A. K. Singh, A. K. Mishra, K. K. Gupta and Y. P. Siwakoti, "High Voltage Gain Bidirectional DC-DC Converters for Supercapacitor Assisted Electric Vehicles: A Review," in *CPSS Transactions on Power Electronics and Applications*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 386-398, December 2022, doi: 10.24295/CPSSTPEA.2022.00035.
- [6]. Z. Sun and S. Bae, "Multiple-Input Soft-Switching DC-DC Converter to Connect Renewable Energy Sources in a DC Microgrid," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 128380-128391, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3227439.
- [7]. A. Elserougi, I. Abdelsalam, A. Massoud and S. Ahmed, "A Non-Isolated Hybrid-Modular DC-DC Converter for DC Grids: Small-Signal Modeling and Control," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 132459-132471, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2941249.

- [8]. M. R. Haque, K. M. A. Salam and M. A. Razzak, "A Modified PI-Controller Based High Current Density DC–DC Converter for EV Charging Applications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 27246-27266, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3258181.
- [9]. H. -J. Choi, K. -W. Heo and J. -H. Jung, "A Hybrid Switching Modulation of Isolated Bidirectional DC-DC Converter for Energy Storage System in DC Microgrid," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 6555-6568, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3138988.
- [10]. J. Yang, R. Li, K. Ma, Y. Wang and P. Xu, "Analysis and Design of Cascaded DC-DC Converter Based Battery Energy Storage System With Distributed Multimode Control in Data Center Application," in *CPSS Transactions on Power Electronics and Applications*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 308-318, September 2022, doi: 10.24295/CPSSTPEA.2022.00028.